

The fall time in gravitational field

Harald Schröer

2015

At Sexl [1] p.71 is indicated that

$$t(R) = \sqrt{\frac{RR_0 \cdot (R_0 - R)}{2MG}} + R_0 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{R_0}{8MG}} \cdot \arccos\left(\frac{2R}{R_0} - 1\right) \quad (1)$$

is the fall time of a mass from R_0 to R . M is the field mass (for example the sun) and G the gravitational constant.

We calculate the fall time from the position R_0 to the sun's surface. R_0 shall be the major semiaxis of the planet's orbit. Then we have the following abbreviations:

a= year

d=day

h=hour

R =sun's radius=696000km

The sun's mass is $1.989 \cdot 10^{30}$ kg

We view the following table with the planet's semiaxes in km.

planet	major semiaxis	fall time
Mercury	58343415	15 d 17 h
Venus	107710920	39 d 11 h
earth	149598500	64 d 14 h
Mars	227389720	121 d 0 h
Jupiter	777912200	2 a 36 d
Saturn	1427169690	5 a 78 d
Uranus	2869299230	14 a 315 d
Neptune	4496930910	29 a 59 d
Pluto	5939060450	44 a 94 d
10-times Pluto's distance	$5.94 \cdot 10^{10}$	1400 a
100-times Pluto's distance	$5.94 \cdot 10^{11}$	44258 a
1000-times Pluto's distance	$5.94 \cdot 10^{12}$	1399569 a

At distances larger than 1000-times Plutodistances the influence of other fixed stars is too strong.

Appendix

We derive the formula (1). The differential equation of a collapsed mass can be written:

$$\frac{d^2 R}{dt^2} = -\frac{GM}{R^2}$$

Then we obtain:

$$\frac{d^2 R}{dt^2} \cdot \frac{dR}{dt} + \frac{GM}{R^2} \cdot \frac{dR}{dt} = 0$$

or:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left[\frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{dR}{dt} \right)^2 - \frac{GM}{R} \right] = 0$$

We follow:

$$\frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{dR}{dt} \right)^2 - \frac{GM}{R} = \text{const.} = -\frac{GM}{R_0}$$

This differential equation can be integrated:

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = \sqrt{2GM \cdot \left(\frac{1}{R} - \frac{1}{R_0} \right)}$$

$$t - t_0 = \int_{R_0}^R \frac{dR}{\left(\frac{dR}{dt}\right)} = - \int_R^{R_0} \frac{dR}{\sqrt{2GM \cdot \left(\frac{1}{R} - \frac{1}{R_0}\right)}}$$

Differentiation from (1) in R with the chain rule:

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{dt(R)}{dR} &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{RR_0^2 - R^2R_0}{2GM} \right)^{-0.5} \cdot \frac{R_0^2 - 2R_0R}{2GM} \\ &\quad + R_0 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{R_0}{8GM}} \cdot \frac{-1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{2R}{R_0} - 1\right)^2}} \cdot \frac{2}{R_0} \\ &= 0.5 \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2GM}}{\sqrt{RR_0^2 - R^2R_0}} \cdot \frac{R_0^2 - 2R_0R}{2GM} \\ &\quad - 2 \cdot \frac{\sqrt{R_0}}{\sqrt{8GM}} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{4R}{R_0} - \frac{4R^2}{R_0^2}}} \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

The first term is denoted with y and the second term with x . We get:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \frac{-\sqrt{R_0}}{\sqrt{8GM}} \cdot \frac{1}{R \cdot \sqrt{\frac{1}{R_0R} - \frac{1}{R_0^2}}} \\ &= \frac{-\sqrt{R_0}}{R \cdot \sqrt{8GM}} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{R_0}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{1}{R} - \frac{1}{R_0}}} \\ &= \frac{-R_0}{R \cdot \sqrt{8GM} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{1}{R} - \frac{1}{R_0}}} = -0.5 \cdot \frac{R_0}{R \cdot \sqrt{2GM \cdot \left(\frac{1}{R} - \frac{1}{R_0}\right)}} \end{aligned}$$

and:

$$\begin{aligned} y &= 0.5 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2GM}{RR_0 \cdot (R_0 - R)}} \cdot \frac{R_0^2 - 2R_0R}{2GM} \\ &= 0.5 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2GM}{R^2R_0^2 \cdot \frac{R_0 - R}{RR_0}}} \cdot \frac{R_0^2 - 2R_0R}{2GM} \\ &= 0.5 \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2GM}}{RR_0 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{1}{R} - \frac{1}{R_0}}} \cdot \frac{R_0^2 - 2R_0R}{2GM} \\ &= 0.5 \cdot \left(\frac{R_0}{R} - 2 \right) \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{2GM \cdot \left(\frac{1}{R} - \frac{1}{R_0}\right)}} \end{aligned}$$

At last we obtain:

$$-\frac{dt(R)}{dR} = x + y = \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2GM \cdot \left(\frac{1}{R} - \frac{1}{R_0}\right)}}$$

Because of the exchange of the integration limits there is a negative sign. The proof is done.

References

- [1] Roman und Hannelore Sexl "Weisse Zwerge - Schwarze Löcher" 2.edition
1990 Vieweg Verlag Brunswick